

Morphotaxonomic Characteristics of Dragonfly, Lesser Emperor, *Anax parthenope* (Selys, 1839) (Odonata: Aeshnidae) at Region Sukkur, Sindh

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ABSTRACT:

Odonates are ecologically important as both predators and prey. Their larvae constitute a natural biological control over mosquito larvae and thus help to control several epidemic diseases like malaria, dengue, filaria etc. In this study; the Dragonfly, *Anax parthenope* (♂:♀) has been identified for the first time at region Sukkur, Sindh - Pakistan. The study was mainly emphasized on morphological differences between male and female specimen. Both male and female specimens were having some same but mostly different characteristics. Like both male and female had large green compound eyes touching dorsally, head was found hypognathous, thorax dark green with visible thoracic segments, male had slightly larger than female wings, bigger in size and more colorful. Which was very rare in insects, fore and hind wings were not similar, forewing narrow and elongated whereas; the hind wings were broad basally, distal part of the wing was yellowish, abdomen was black dorsally and ventrally but found greenish from lateral side. It was concluded that there was a lot of potential to explore Odonata fauna of this region. The climate and topography of this area along with lot of natural pastures and aquatic bodies support dragonflies' life and biology. However, due to rapid increase in urbanization, suitable habitats of odonata were disappearing at an alarming rate. Thus, only single specie was found. Further surveys and necessary conservation measures were also adopted, therefore, suggested as need of the day to utilize it, in right direction after knowing its species complex.

Keyword: Rainfall, summer season, predator, hard toothed, lateral, ventral and dorsal sides.

INTRODUCTION

Almost everywhere you look, you'll find one or dozens of the six-legged critters called insects, most successful creatures to date, scientists have catalogued about 1.5 million species of organisms on the planet, with insects making up about two-thirds of this bounty. Dragonflies are belonging to the class Insecta, Order Odonata and Sub order Anisoptera. They are divided into three suborders the more delicate weakly flying damselflies (Zygoptera), the more robust dragonflies (Anisoptera) and a relict group of primitive dragonflies (Anisozygoptera). Dragonflies also possess medicinal properties and are used in medicine preparation in some countries [1]. Odonata is one of the oldest groups of winged insects found today. Approximately; 6000 species and subspecies to 630 genera in 28 families are well known from all over the world. Dragonflies are key components of freshwater ecosystem. The larvae serve as food for freshwater fish and the soft bodies of the general are fed by birds [2]. Odonates are ecologically important as both predators and prey. Their larvae constitute a natural biological control over mosquito larvae and thus help to control several epidemic diseases like malaria, dengue, filaria etc. The single adult of dragonfly may eat 300-400 gnats each day [3]. Dragonflies' characteristics make them suitable subjects for biological research, especially for studies on behavior and ecology [4]. They vary in their sensitivity to different sorts of pollution and are thus used as indicator of water pollution [5]. Total of 17 dragonfly species with 11 Zygoptera and 10 Anisoptera that representing six families were recorded at 21 sites, a total of 174 individuals representing 11 species such as; *I. graellsii*, *C. caerulea* and *L. viridis* were the most abundant dragonfly species [6]. Females of all the species consumed much

greater number of insect pests as compared with male [7].

The adults of some species visit important crop fields like cotton and rice in search of their food and in this way helps in controlling insect pests of these cultivated crops [8]. This makes them having great economic values and thus they have been center of global researchers during recent past they also make beautiful biodiversity on earth [9]. Dragonflies are found on every continent except Antarctica. Dragonflies are powerful and agile fliers, capable of migrating across oceans, moving in any direction, and changing direction suddenly [10]. The vortex interaction was observed between forewing and hind wing of dragonfly in hovering flight [11]. Similarly, [12] effects of blood was in veins of dragonfly wing on the vibration characteristics and [13] found ecological network for conserving dragonflies. The continental scale conservation prioritization of African dragonflies highlighted [14], and damselflies (Zygoptera: Odonata) of Pakistan [15] with the Odonata naiads of Potohar plateau, Punjab, Pakistan [5], as; *Calicnemia fortis* sp. nov. from Pakistan (Odonata: Zygoptera: Platycnemididae) [16]. The dragonflies are not found everywhere they have selected habitats and are confined to their niche [17]. They are usually found around marshes, lakes, ponds, streams and wetlands because their nymph aquatic [18]. A dragonfly namely; Lesser emperor, *Anax parthenope* (Selys, 1839) [19] is the family Aeshnidae found in Southern Europe, north Africa and Asia. In the east of its Asian range such as; China, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Japan, Korea, Southern Far East Russia and South Siberia, the subspecies; *Anax parthenope julius* (Brauer, 1865) occurs, which might prove to be a distinct species. Length around 71mm, breeds in ponds and small lakes and can tolerate brackish water, commonly seen from June to September [20]. A.

parthenope happens in much of southern and central Europe as; Mediterranean islands, across Asia to Japan, Korean Peninsula and China, and north Africa and was first seen in Great Britain [21]. It has often seen patrolling around ponds, lakes and other still (polluted) water [22]. Odonates 68 species have been founded in Pakistan [23], includes *Anax parthenope*. The objective of the present study is to explore dragonfly lesser emperor, *A. parthenope* fauna for the first time at this region for awareness and edification.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and preservation of *A. parthenope*

The dragonflies (male and female) were collected from region Sukkur, Sindh-Pakistan during the winter season, 2017 at noon time from polluted stagnant water because, at the time the temperature was normal. The samples were taken through the hand net stroke method to capture. The captured dragon flies were isolated and male as well female were kept separately in vials or insect collection box to do not mix up, rub, breaking or damaged. The samples were only taken of this dragon fly to check out the morphotaxonomic variations to others, living in same vicinity. After collection the dragonflies were fainted using chloroform than photographs were taken. The morphological features and measurements were recorded of both the male and female of this species at the field conditions and latter on brought under the Entomology laboratory conditions at Department of Zoology, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur. During the research work, it was only focused over this kind of specie because the most predominant specie was found throughout the winter season because of mosquitoes' appearance and breeding season at this region. The climate of this region is classified as a subtropical prairieland (low-latitude dry), where rainfall and other precipitation has no distinct peak months. In this region, month of June was warmest with an average temperature of 45°C at noon time. January was coldest with an average temperature of 16°C, respectively. At the time of collection temperature was approximately 20°C with the relative humidity 15%. The data about prescribed a biotic factors' were measured with the digital hygrometer and finally the overall means were calculated.

Identification of *A. parthenope*

The male as well female collected specimens were subjected to morpho-metric analysis of this specie. Necessity to analysis the details of predatory dragonfly even there was male and female specimens were observed and the photographs were made with the

high resolution photographs camera. The dragonfly was identified as dragonfly lesser emperor, *Anax parthenope* (Selys, 1839) (Odonata: Aeshnidae) through its taxonomic and morphological characteristics. It is mostly found in Southern Europe, North Africa, and Asia regions of the globe.

Morphometry and Photography of *A. parthenope*

The different parts of the predatory dragon flies such as; head, thorax, abdomen, wings and their lateral, ventral and dorsal sides were dissected and measured with common scale ruler, then photographs were taken by 8 mp of camera, after identification and measurement the specimens were placed on top of a bland white sheet of paper. Finally, these specimens were kept at department of Zoology for future coverage.

RESULTS

The wings formation of female was (5cm) when compared with (4.7cm) to male whereas; the wings width of female was (1.5cm) and male (1.3cm) (♀:♂). Thus, the abdomen of female was observed (4.4cm) when compared with male (4.2cm) and thoracic region of female (1.5cm) and male (1.1cm), respectively (Table - 1).

During the research study it was observed that the specimen of female and male (♀:♂) had large green compound eyes touching dorsally, head was hypognathous, thorax was dark green with visible thoracic segments, female has slightly larger than male ones. Wings of females were also slightly larger, fore and hind wings were not similar, forewing narrow and elongated and hind wings were broad basally, distal part of the wing was yellowish (female had darker yellow) in color. Abdomen was black dorsally and ventrally but greenish from lateral side in some specimen bluish lateral side was also observed but the study was mainly emphasized on morphological differences between female and male specimen (Table -2).

Morpho-metric observation revealed that the head region of male dragonfly as; dorsal part or size in vertical (0.7cm) and horizontal (0.6cm) whereas; the same was observed in female one. The male thoracic region of dragonfly, *A. parthenope* was measured as (1.5cm) and female (1.7cm) with the male abdomen region (4.8cm) and female (4.10cm). Thusly, the male wing dorsal side (fore and hind wing) =4.7cm was observed and female =4.10cm, respectively. Further the Morphotaxonomic characteristics of dragonfly, Lesser Emperor, *Anax parthenope* (Selys, 1839) (Odonata: Aeshnidae) (♂:♀) dorsal, lateral and ventral sides were observed under laboratory conditions (Fig. 1).

Table -1. Morpho-metric description of female and male of *A. parthenope* (♀:♂)

Parameters	Measurements	
	Female	Male
Wings	5.0cm	4.7cm
Wings width	1.5cm	1.3cm
Abdomen	4.4cm	4.2cm
Thorax	1.5cm	1.1cm

Table -2. Comparative morphological parameters of *Anax parthenope* (♀:♂)

Parameter	Female	Male	Remarks
Wings	Having smaller dark yellow shed at distal part of wing.	Having larger light yellow shed at the distal part of wing.	Slightly varied
Abdomen	Number of segments have light brownish to green in color with blackish dorso ventral lines.	Segment -1 and 2 (S1 and S2) has bright blue color.	Dissimilar
Legs	Black with more hair like structures.	Black with hair like structures.	Comparable
Thorax	Yellow with some dark green patches	Yellow with some dark green	Similar

	and visible thoracic segments.	patches and visible thoracic segments.	
Eyes	Green eyes touching dorsally.	Green eyes touching dorsally.	Similar

Fig. 1. Morphotaxonomic characteristics of dragonfly, Lesser Emperor, *Anax parthenope* (Selys, 1839) (Odonata: Aeshnidae) (♂ :♀) dorsal, lateral and ventral sides

Head region of male. Dorsal side; size of head: vertical =0.7cm; horizontal =0.6cm.	Lateral side	Ventral side
Female: Dorsal side; size of head: vertical =0.7cm; horizontal = 0.6cm.		
Male thoracic region =1.5cm		
Female thoracic region =1.7cm		
Male abdomen region = 4.8cm		

Female abdomen region =4.10cm		
Male wing dorsal side (Fore and hind wings) =4.7cm	Ventral side (Fore and hind wings)	Male adult
Female wing dorsal side (Fore and hind wings) = 4.9cm	Female wing ventral side (fore and hind wings)	Female adult
Habitat of <i>Anax parthenope</i> in stagnant water at region Sukkur (photo: Sahito and Bhutto)		

DISCUSSION

The specie of dragonfly Lesser Emperor, *Anax parthenope* has been identified for the first time at this region Sukkur, Sindh – Pakistan that emphasized on morphological differences between male and female ones. The literature survey suggests that this kind of specie has not been reported in this region before and morphological analysis have never been done. Although, several studies has been conducted in different regions. Reviewing the previous research work done on dragonflies in Pakistan. Like this; the researcher collected and identified 46 species and subspecies belonging to 24 genera of 6 subfamilies of anisoptrous dragonflies from various localities of Pakistan [24]. Besides, the recorded 6 anisopterous species from districts Mansehra (Khyber Pakhtonkhwa, Pakistan) were observed [8]. In another study, [9] recorded 22 dragonfly species from Murree hills (district Rawalpindi, Pakistan) and 21 dragonfly species belonging to 14 genera and 4 families from Khyber Pakhtonkhwa province of Pakistan [25]. Besides, 13 dragonflies' species from Gilgit, Baltistan and Kashmir region were reported [10, 26] and 35 belonging to 22 genera of 12 subfamilies in 3 families from Punjab [27].

Male and female specimens had some of them relevant and few of them irrelevant morphological characteristics such as; male and female had large green compound eyes touching dorsally with the hypognathous head whereas; fore and hind wings were dissimilar to both of couple. In another study, [28] recorded 6 anisopterous species from the rice fields in the districts Poonch and Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. While total of 37 specimens belonging to 02 family, 6 genera and 7 species were collected and identified. Among the collected fauna family Aeshnadae with one species *Hemianax ephippiger* belong to one genera and Libellulidae with 6 species viz, *Crocothemis servilia*, *Orthetrum glucum*, *Orthetrum pruinosum*, *palpopluera sexmaculata*, *Rhodothemis rufa* and *Pantala flavescens* belonging to 5 genera were recorded from District Baramulla and Bandipora, Jammu and Kashmir. Details for the collected material i.e. valid names, their synonyms, measurements of different body parts; abdomen, forewing and hindwing, richness and abundance were discussed [29]. Odonata of Azad Jammu and Kashmir was also reported by [30]. Analyze of 35 dragonfly species belonging to 22 genera of 12 subfamilies in 3 families from Punjab [27]. The total of 17 dragonfly species (11 Zygoptera and ten Anisoptera) representing six families were recorded at 21 sites [6]. Further, Odonates 68 species has also been founded in Pakistan, which was published in 2016 founded species also includes *Anax parthenope* [31, 32, 33].

There is huge potential to explore Odonata fauna of this region. The climate and topography of this area along with lot of natural pastures and aquatic bodies support dragonflies' life and biology. However, due to rapid increase in urbanization, suitable habitats of odonata were disappearing at an alarming rate. In 2008 and 2009, Lesser Emperor *Anax parthenope* has been found at five localities in Latvia [34]. The dragonfly is a new species for Latvian fauna. Dragonfly species, 59 of 9 families have been recorded in Latvia so far, inter alia two or three temporary immigrants and one species with unclear status [35]. The aforementioned review of research work is a scattered work of different scientists in some areas of Pakistan whereas, the present study was a unique and comprehensive as it was done on the morphological characteristics of particular species (both male and female). Further, [36] evaluated that the *A. parthenope* was widespread over most of Europe, from the Iberian Peninsula to Russia, and from southernmost islands to Lithuania. Its range extends also through Asia and Africa reaching Japan, China, and Sahara. And also their

mating behavior was observed on leaves of rooted plants of stagnant water. In some specimen abdomen with bluish lateral side was also observed, as the completes its nymphal life in water so the modification is may be due to different pollutants that are present in that stagnant water where from the specimens were collected. The adults of *A. parthenope* by the use of entomological net, or recorded in the field by direct observations and *Sympetrum fonscolombii* (Selys, 1840), [37, 38] and the vortex interactions between forewing and hindwing of dragonfly in hovering flight [39, 40] was also initiated.

CONCLUSION

Keeping in view, the results of current study, it is concluded that there is a lot of potential to explore Odonata fauna of upper region, Sukkur - Sindh. The climate and topography of this area along with lot of natural pastures and aquatic bodies support dragonflies' life and biology. However, due to rapid increase in urbanization, suitable habitats of Odonata are disappearing at an alarming rate. Thus only single specie was found. Further surveys and necessary conservation measures are, therefore, suggested as need of the day to utilize it, in right direction after knowing its species complex. It is also concluded that the male of the dragonfly, Lesser Emperor, *Anax parthenope* (Selys, 1839) (Odonata: Aeshnidae) is bigger in size and more colorful which is very rare in insects.

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Being an important predator of crop pests, dengue and malarial vector (mosquitoes) and other harmful insects, awareness should be generated in local public through electronic and print media to save it from injudicious use of pesticides in fields. Steps should be taken to minimize the chances of disturbances and loss of natural habitats of Odonata, as it adversely affects species composition and its abundance.

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